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Ethnic Diversity and Democratic Challenges in Africa: An Evaluation of J. S. Mill's Utilitarianism as a Remedy to the Challenges

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Abstract

This paper analyzes and examines the challenges associated with various democratic ideologies in Africa. Democratic practices vary across continents, and Africa as a continent is of no exception. The effectiveness of these democratic practices in Africa often depends on the regional and national contexts. Many African countries have adopted the forms of representative democracy, where the citizens elect their representatives to make and exhibit decisions on their behalf. However, the effectiveness of this practices in Africa has been overwhelmed with anomalies that have hindered national interests such that it has paved way for both economic and political crisis in African democracies in contemporary African societies. This socio-political ideology has not only fuelled crisis in many African states but it has led to marginalization and favouritism both in political and economic contexts. In order to rescue further crisis by this popular ideology as embedded in majoritarian/representative democratic practices as evident in most African democratic states, this paper employs Mill's utilitarian principle that advocates for individual rights, social reforms and that which it is democratic, qualitative and participatory to solve the issues of ethnic diversity in African democracies. The paper submits that, amidst different ethnic diversity in African

democracies, there is a need for individual participation through participatory democracy. The paper concludes that participatory democracy will not only strengthen democracy and its practices in various African states, it will also institutionalize a core democratic principle that upholds unity, happiness and tolerance amidst differences in ethnic diversities in African heritage.

Keywords: Africa, democracy, ethnic diversity, J. S. Mill's Utilitarianism

Introduction

Ethnic diversity presents significant challenges to democratic governance and practices to African democracies. Overtime, it has aided and fostered social tensions, ethnic-based conflicts, nepotism, and political fragmentation to African democracies. From antecedent, African states have been occupied with multi-ethnicity. Amidst this multi-ethnicity in African democratic practices have been filled with ethnic diversity of which it is unhealthy for democratic practices in Africa. Marginalization, discrimination, favouritism, tribalism and by extension, religious conflicts are some of the difficulties imposed on African democracies.

Ethnic diversity as embedded in African democracies has led to differences and obstruction in interests and from the individual and collective perspectives. Hassan (2018) argues that ethnic diversity associated with politics is "particularly obvious in areas like voting, distribution of political offices, employment and government general patronage of the citizens". Deductively, differences in interests from the holistic and individual points of view have escalated to the national level which has also served as threats to the national unity in multi-ethnic societies. Series of scholars and philosophers have proposed possible solutions to the issue of ethnic diversities in African democracies through consensual, representative, direct, indirect types of democracies to solving the issue of ethnic diversity in African democracies. Of all these types of democracies, representative democracy has been commonly used to solving the issue of ethnic diversity. It is imperative to note that the role of representative democracy cannot be de-emphasized but not fully adequate to solving the challenges of ethnic diversity in African democracies.

This paper evaluates J. S. Mill's utilitarianism as a remedy to the challenges posed by ethnic diversity to African democracies. It is worth knowing that, Mill's concept of utilitarian principle holds that the common good should maximize overall happiness. It emphasizes the greatest happiness principle

as a gateway to promoting the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people in pleasure and moral. His views on liberty and representative government can be logically deduced from his utilitarian principle where he advocated for a government that is not only democratic and qualitative, but also participatory. By exploring Mill's utilitarianism in the context of African democracies, the paper submits that representative kind of democracy though adequate, but it is not totally sufficient to eradicate the ethnic diversity in African democracies. Hence, there is need to employ participatory democracy to supplement representative democracy in African societies. This paper analyzes and examines the challenges associated with various democratic ideologies in Africa. With Mill's utilitarian principle which advocates for democracy, individual rights, social reforms, qualitative and that which is participatory, the paper posits that the challenges of ethnic diversity to African democracies can be curbed to the barest minimum if not totally eradicated.

J. S. Mill's Utilitarianism: An Understanding

One of the most important English-speaking philosophers in the nineteenth century that his thoughts and reflections covered philosophical issues was John Stuart Mill (1806-1873). As a philosopher, economist, moral and political philosopher, his thoughts are still very relevant and are widely acknowledged as one of the strongest and most persuasive justifications of empiricism and a liberal political perspective on society and culture. One of the aims of J. S. Mill is to elucidate the notion of utilitarianism via the lens of utility, which gauges the morality and standard of an individual or society as that which brings happiness through a qualitative approach. As observed by Zachariah et al (2024, p. 3737, Mill places high premiums not only on human beings or the quantity of their happiness but also on the quality of individual members who collectively form society. It is evident that the basis and rational justification for Mill's utilitarianism lies in the happiness of the individual and the society at large.

The promulgation of happiness is undoubtedly, the ultimate foundation of Mill's moral principle and political philosophy. The formation of good and equitable society with people of goodwill should rest on the utilitarian principle maxim which states that the greatest happiness should be of the greatest number, should be used to measure the perfection of society, people, and desires towards the interests of individuals that are holistically

inclined. With this, individuals will be able to realize their potentials to make decisions, exhibit their thoughts, and exercise their human rights abilities gearing towards liberation and the common good of the society cum wellbeing of other people. To corroborate this, Njoku (2019, p. 358), sees mill's utilitarianism postulation as that which refers to the ability of individuals to discover and develop their rights, liberties and powers towards the exhibition of their human abilities as directed towards liberation and independence as a crucial requirement towards leading to and living a good, worthy and dignified life. Zachariah et al reiterated that "Mill's definition of human happiness transcends not only the mere increase in quantity but also the quality of goods enjoyed since the *Homo sapiens* are capable of demonstrating intellectual moral pleasures and that prove them superior to other species of mammals" (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3738). Happiness is all that matters, and happiness simply is pleasure and the absence of pain. He states this very clearly: By happiness is intended pleasure, and the absence of pain; by unhappiness pain, and the privation of pleasure. (Mill, 1976, p. 55).

It is worthy to note that, Mill proffered a new account of pleasure when he asked why it is objectionable to put a human life and a pig on a par. The rationale behind this is that human beings are capable of much more valuable experiences than pigs" (Mulgan, 2007, p. 23). Since happiness is intended pleasure, and absence of pain, Mill made a distinction between higher and lower pleasures. With this, Mill's principle of utility recognizes some kinds of pleasure that more desirable and valuable than others. It is imperative to note that, in the quest of desiring and valuing one thing over the other, the quality should be considered as well as the quantity. However, the establishment of pleasure should be quality-based. According to Mill, people who have experienced both higher and lower pleasures prefer the higher. So higher pleasures are better. That is why Mill contended that:

It is better to be a human being dissatisfied than a pig satisfied; better to be Socrates dissatisfied than a fool satisfied. And if the fool, or the pig, has a different opinion, it is because they only know their own side of the question. The other party to the comparison knows both sides (Mill, 1976, p. 9).

From the above, it is logically deduced that Mill's utility sees happiness as not just a particular thing that exists in the mind but, also, a quality of life

in the organized and active expression of one's power and capacities (Mukherjee & Ramaswamy, 2007, p. 108). It is a function identified with "good, human endeavour, virtue or excellence" (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3738). Mill further reiterated that social wellbeing should be a priority to all men that are in possession of good will, freedom, integrity. These attributes do not only contribute to human happiness rather, they are also intrinsically good in themselves (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3738). The only thing that man should aim at is happiness which should not be a means to an end but a means in themselves. Mill contends that "the chief end of life is the happiness and dignity of man" which is commensurable with quantitative pleasure irrespective of its quality (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3739). Not only that, he ascribed happiness to be human perfection, cultivation of moral virtues, total control over one's appetites and desires and recognition of individual and collective interests.

The concept of freedom and, by extension, happiness goes beyond the absence of restraints. Be it as it may, the fact that individuals in the society have the ability to exhibit good choices that are genuine, desired and quality-based not only for themselves or their needs, but, for their immediate society makes them more utilitarian. It is evident however, that, Mill's principle of utility that is well grounded in the happiness of the greatest number of people, that is qualitative and pleasure-seeking serves as foundation for his other philosophical discourse most especially, on democracy, education and liberty as ideologies respectively.

A Historical and Philosophical Account of Democracies in Africa

The kind of democratic ideology which a state practices determines and influences the level of growth and development. From this assertion, it is deduced that democracies in Africa varies right from the pre-colonial era to the contemporary Africa. There are different democratic ideologies which includes but not limited to the following: socialist, consensual, majoritarian and representative, and participatory democracy.

Socialist Democracy

The effort to rediscover the true African socialism is geared towards the fight for independence by the African nationalists. The African socialism is seen as the collective ideology among the Africans and the African societies at large. This holistic ideology made traditional African system of

governance differs from other continental political ideologies. The socialist form of democracy was championed by Julius Nyerere in Tanzania. In a bid to rediscover a true political ideology peculiar to Tanzania, Nyerere advocated for a communal base ideology. Here, the African socialism postulated by Nyerere goes along with Karl Marx ideology. This is also known as Marxist ideology. Marx proposed that the best stage or political ideology that any society should attain or at best practice is communalism. The word *Ujamaa* has coined by Julius Nyerere means brotherhood or familyhood. This concept of *Ujamaa* was Arusha declaration was made known in February 1967 (El Saadawi, 2010, p. 13). According to El Saadawi, (2010, p. 13), the Arusha Declaration is a very simple document in a sense that it is not a profound theory; but a way of dealing with practical problems which arose after independence. The Arusha declaration has two parts *vis a vis*: the first part is on the TANU creed and the second part is on the policy of socialism. As argued by Njiofor (2018, p. 2), a strong veritable index of traditional African socialism is embedded in altruism, transparent communal promotion of mutual support, pursuit of common good, well-being, and wholesome flourishing of all the other members of the community. Nyerere's socialist ideology prioritizes the 'We' than 'I' in decision-making process. In other words, the idea of communalism is embedded in traditional African societies which places the community above the individuals. To sum it up, the famous phrase is: for 'we exist' therefore 'I am'.

Consensual Democracy

The idea of consensual democracy was brought into limelight by Kwasi Wiredu in his work titled *Democracy and Consensus in African Traditional Politics: A Plea for a Non-Party Polity (1996)* (Fasina, 2025, p. 1). Wiredu's consensual form of democracy was borne out of the precolonial consensual form of governance. According to him, society in the precolonial era was either with a centralized mode of governance or with a less centralized mode of governance. The societies with centralized mode of governance or authority is controlled by a government machinery. This government machinery which according to Wiredu may be regarded as government (Fasina, 2025, p. 19, Wiredu, 1997, p. 304). He explains further that, for a proper analysis on his notion of consensual democracy, Wiredu limits his account of traditional notion of consensus to the political system of

governance among the people of *Ashantis* in Ghana. The Ashantis according to Wiredu, are a matrilineal group with centralized authority with units “consisting of all people in town or village having a common female ancestor, which, as a rule, is quite a considerable body of persons” (Wiredu, 1997, p. 305). In this society, consensual form of democracy is taken to be a political ideology that utilizes consensus as a natural instrument in decisions and social interaction among the Ashantis. Before consensus can be reached at, the precolonial African societies employed communalism as an ideology and in principle in execution and action via means of free discussion varying from series of disagreement to agreement on salient issues that either makes or mar the society in question. What this means is that, consensus in the traditional African societies employs dialogue, conflicts, negotiation, reconciliation, and resolution on diverse issues among diverse opinions. It is important to note that, Wiredu calls for the return of consensual form of democracy in the contemporary African societies as a result of the failures that majoritarian or representative democracy has caused.

Participatory Democracy

Participatory democracy is an ideological system of governance which emphasizes on active, substantial and true inclusion of individuals that occupies the society in decision-making processes. Participatory democratic system of governance embraces citizens’ engagement, inclusivity, transparency, accountability. Participatory democracy was championed by Amilcar Cabral. His approach was shaped by the experiences in Guinea-Bissau and Cape Verde’s in their quest and struggle for independence. The participatory kind of democracy he advocated for is that which embraces the bottom-up approach, mobilization and awareness, true inclusivity, and self-reliance. He contends that social justice can only be achieved through this socio-political ideology (Gomes, 2023, p. 6).

The Problem of Ethnic Diversity in African Democracies

As reiterated in the introductory part of this paper that, ethnic diversity presents significant challenges to democratic governance and practices to African democracies. Hence, important to state here that, without ‘ethnicity’ there cannot exist ‘ethnic diversity’. Therefore, ethnicity is conceived to be ‘a conglomeration of persons or group living in a particular society, characterized by a shared unique and fundamental identity that is well-

grounded in in common heritage, ancestry, affinity, language, cultural practices, and often, shared goals or values'. Ethnicity has been viewed from different perspective. In line with this, as cited by Agbu (2011, p. 8) that Anugwom (2000, p. 64) sees ethnicity as "arising from a situation where a group of people, no matter how small, with different cultural and linguistic attributes from those of its neighbours, use this as the basis for solidarity and interaction with others". What this means is that, the ingredients that makes the formation of ethnicity are identity, sociocultural consciousness, linguistic attributes, solidarity, interaction and cultural point of view. Consequently, democracies in Africa are overwhelmed by ethnicity and by extension ethnic diversity. Factually, ethnic diversity as embedded in African democracies has degenerated to marginalization, discrimination, favouritism, tribalism and by extension, religious conflicts. Deductively, differences in interests from the holistic and individual points of view which, most times, escalates to the national level also serves as threats to the national unity in multi-ethnic societies. Since African countries have gained independence, it may interest one to know however, that ethnic diversity has made the 'identification with common good' a difficult task to achieve. It is now evident that democracies in Africa, most especially representative like of democracy is been run and triumph on ethnic politics. Furthermore, ethnic politics now dominates over substantive representation and participation of individuals and representatives in the society. This kind of democratic ideology can easily be interpreted as that democracy which is run on 'survival of the fittest of the ethnic majority'. In line with this, Salawu and Hassan (2018) argues that ethnic diversity and politics is "particularly obvious in areas like voting, distribution of political offices, employment and government general patronage of the citizens". As part of the principles that upholds representative kind of democracy practiced in most of the African countries which relies on equality, liberty, constitution, law, and fundamental human rights are now been jeopardized by the so-called elites who are in charge of the economic and political power of the state respectively. For the sake of history, ethnic diversity has hindered the growth and development of majoritarian or representative democracy in the time past. I shall be considering some core factors that are problematic to democracies in Africa most especially representative democracy, which makes not totally adequate for practice.

To begin with, ethnic majoritarianism is a core problem that is a threat to democratic practices in Africa. Putting into context, the ethnic and cultural diversity is one of the major challenges Nigeria as a country in West Africa is facing. The three dominant ethnic groups in Nigeria are the Yoruba, Hausa/Fulani and the Igbos. As contended by Ali and Yahaya (2019, p. 70):

Hausa-Fulani ethnic groups are the majority in the North and are Muslims, the Yoruba in the South are the majority and significant percent of them are Muslims and Igbos in the East are the majority and significant percent of them are Christians, most of the time, they used ethnicity and religion to manipulate political process to their personal and selfish advantages and most often than not it result to ethnic violent conflict. These three major ethnic groups in Nigeria are competing for the scarce resources in an unhealthy rivalry.

Differences in ethnicity has made one ethnic group pointing fingers to the other for gross misconduct, tribal war, unfair sharing of resources, funds mismanagement, unjust resource allocation, abuse of power, chaos cause to mention but a few. These aforementioned factors have degenerated to social, economic and political problem propagated with #EndSARS, #EndBadGovernance, Niger-Delta Militancy, and Fulani-Herder conflicts. The interests of the minority ethnic groups are not been catered for in the quest of making collective decisions that favours all and sundry in the process. With this, ethnic majoritarianism poses a problem to democratic process in Nigeria. Another typical instance of how ethnic majoritarianism has threatened democratic process in Africa is that of ethnic favoritism in Kenya. As far back as 2007 when election was conducted and it was deduced that the poll they had was along ethnic line that led to election rigging and manipulation. This made post-election violence to occur wherein over 1,000 individuals were killed along ethnic lines. Furthermore, ethnic diversity has also posed threats to democratic processes in South Africa as in the case of Xenophobia, the Tigray conflict in Ethiopia, power struggle between the Tutsis and Hutus in Rwanda, ethnic militia politics between North and South Sudan to mention but a few.

Political zoning arrangement is another core factor that poses a threat to democratic practices in Africa. Be it as it may, in the process of raising equality and balance between the ethnic groups, it sometimes deepens ethnic consciousness and favoritism. Often times, as in the case of Nigeria,

this has led to protest against bad governance, hardship, economic instability with ethnic undertones. To stress this further, Ali and Yahaya reiterated that: the country experienced civil war in 1967-1970, violent ethnic conflict in different parts of the country such as Zangon Kataf crisis in Kaduna state, Tiv/Jukun ethnic conflict in Taraba State, Hausa-Fulani and Birom ethnic conflict in Plateau state, Ife/Modakeke ethnic conflict in Oyo state, Igbo/Hausa-Fulani in Kano and others ethnic conflicts occurred has threaten the corporate existence of Nigeria as a Nation-State (Ali and Yahaya, 2019, p. 70).

J. S. Mill's Utilitarianism as a Remedy to the Challenges of Ethnic Diversity in African Democracies

Ethnic diversity cum ethnic conflict have become a perennial problem that most African countries faces which fuelled by majoritarian or representative democracy that fails to put the collective and substantive interest of the people into consideration. It is now evident that what the citizens want is their active participation in politics and democratic procedures. They no longer request for or rely on representation that does not cater for their interests substantively. The polity is now been dominated by political elites who chooses to make decisions that will in-turn becomes laws without proper and adequate consultations from their constituents. This is one of the reasons why Kwasi Wiredu in his work titled *Democracy and Consensus in African Traditional Politics: A Plea for a Non-Party Polity (1996)* frowned at majoritarian or representative form of democracy as that which do not cater for the interest of the minority. The political elites now deprive the citizens of what they are entitled to using deceit, 'playing a game-blame' of failure ascribing it to one political elite, ethnic group, creed, region or the other to propagate political propaganda shifting from what is dutiful of them.

Since the citizens now advocates for a system of governance which caters for individual rights, social reforms and that which it is democratic, qualitative and participatory to solve the issues of ethnic diversity in African democracies, there is a need for participatory democracy be complemented with representative or majoritarian democracy. In other words, the only way to go however, is for the political elites to imbibe the principles of participatory kind of democracy in the majoritarian or representative kind of democracy. In line with this, Ogbiniyi and Ojiji (2021, p. 18), argues that

“the term democracy as a general project must be anchored on different facets of the participation of citizens, accountability of rulers, open economies and just societies”. The scholars cited some African leaders who misused power vested in them at expense of their own good and their close allies. Robert Mugabe of Zimbabwe “deprived citizens of their chance at wealth through his notorious land reforms that only favored his close allies and also illegally sent soldiers to engage in the Congolese civil war which set the economy back as he raced to please returning veterans who weaken the opposition in order to keep him in power” (Ogbiniyi and Ojiji, 2021, p. 18). Not only that, Idi Amin Dada, a former president of Uganda expelled all Indians in Uganda as he deemed them leeches to the growing economy and ignored the participation of citizens as he ruled Uganda for 9 years without any elections (Ogbiniyi and Ojiji, 2021, p. 18). It may interest one to know however, that these political elites fail to put the interest of ethnic group and various individuals decisions and yearnings into consideration. Consequently, sub-Saharan African countries now exhibits incompetent democratic practices leading to overthrown of democratically elected elites by militaries, with the seizure and capture of territories by secessionists and terrorists. Berman (2010, p. 26) wrote that:

the winner-take-all outcome of elections in systems without proportional representation in most states, increased smaller communities’ fear of domination by larger groups, the increasingly inequitable distribution of wealth, and their ultimate exclusion from access to the state. Instead of reducing corruption, democratization allowed it to reach new heights as newly elected politicians sought ‘our turn to eat’, and the politics of the belly revealed the personal, materialistic and opportunistic character of politics and the relative unimportance of ideology, principal or policy in the circumscribed political arena.

The inclusivity and participatory kind of democracy is long gone and no longer in workability. That is why the propagation and spread of the idea or watchword of “socio-cultural boundaries of ethnic groups and their claims to being the native inhabitants of national territory became objects of growing conflict with regards to both political participation and access to material benefits” (Berman, 2010, p. 27). This, overtime, has promulgated a lot of conflict and ethnic bias over adequate representation and fair and equal sharing. Human rights violation, ethnic conflicts and other forms of

unrest in the sub-Saharan African countries for instance, are products of weak political and democratic institutions instituted in the various countries. It is important to note however, that, the weak institution occupied by these incompetent elites or office holders with their incompetent and unjust decisions turned laws are now been imposed on the citizens through the usage of state instruments such as security forces such as the police to tame the citizens or ethnic groups not to protest as enshrined in the constitution against bad governance, unfair sharing of resources, tribal sentiments, and other forms of atrocities propagated by these political elites.

It is lucid that, to rescue African states from further ethnic conflicts, economic instability and political shambles, there is need for a thorough consideration of democratic principles that is embedded with true participation of individuals and ethnic groups amidst diversities which is aimed at social reform. Undoubtedly, there is a need to employ Mills's utilitarianism. Although, to get rid of ambiguity, mill proposed a representative democracy. His representative democracy enhances quality, individual rights, individual participation and social reform. Mill's utilitarianism if applied will guide African democratic ideologies and procedures in having a just and equitable society, policy-making, and resource distribution among various ethnic groups be it majority or minority. Mill's formation and translation of utilitarianism lay emphasis on the qualitative aspects of individuals happiness and the protection of individual rights (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3751), which is significant as a remedy in solving ethnic diversities in African democracies. An application of Mill's utilitarianism would solve if not eradicate ethnic conflicts and promotes "intellectual and cultural growth in addition to economic progress, which is essential to the nation-building process and national development (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3751).

More so, the quest for human rights and autonomy is very much significant in Mill's utilitarianism. The rights and privileges of many individuals have been trampled upon. As contended by Mill on the rights of individuals as it amounts to happiness, he reiterated that individual rights are essential for overall happiness (Mill, 1863). For there to be collective interests that will in-turn leads to happiness, the individual's interest and happiness must firstly, be taken care of. With that, collective belongings that is tied together with various ethnic groups amidst their diversities based on differences in

language, history, culture, race, norms, values, traditions, religion, nationality and ancestral descent would be achievable to foster a stable democratic practice that will benefit all and sundry. The contribution of ethnic group cannot be underestimated in any democracy. As every individual in the society is attached to one ethnic group or the other. This is fervently explained by Ali and Yahaya in their work that “of all the groups that man attaches himself to, ethnic groups seem the most encompassing and enduring. It can be a building block, but also a potential stumbling block on the road to modernity and no ethnic group remain isolated” (Ali and Yahaya, 2019, p. 70). They contended further that ethnic group sharp and mould an individual perception with a sense of belongings in the society.

Consequently, Mill’s utilitarianism and democratic theory embodies participatory democracy. As such, through participation of individuals and ethnic groups in decision-making process, it will aid and promote the notion of inclusive governance that is of greater and common good that is geared towards societal well-being, economic stability, accountability cum transparency, and human rights protection. If this Mill’s utilitarianism is been put into consideration, it will situate a balance and equality majority rule and minority rights idea. Putting Nigeria as a case study, according to Zachariah et al, Mill’s idea of inclusive and participatory governance calls for reforms that strengthen political freedom and safeguard minority rights while working towards broader societal objectives (Zachariah et al., 2024, p. 3751). They explained further that finding a balance between majority rule and minority rights is a crucial issue in Nigerian democratic governance. Mill’s utility suggests that policies should not only cater to the majority but also consider the needs of minority groups. Inclusive governance strategies, such as federal character principles and affirmative action, strive to give diverse ethnic and religious communities a say in political decision making. This approach aligns with Mill’s belief in safeguarding individual rights while enhancing societal well-being.

Conclusion

Many African countries with the spirit and ideology of majoritarian/representative democratic practices have taken majority rule ideology as a suitable and preferrable system of governance. Unfortunately, it has been established that this ideology has not only degenerated to

several issues which threatens national unity in many African states which in-turn leads to problems that appears to be perennial in nature. To rescue African states from these continued problems dominating African states this paper posits that there is a need for true inclusion and sense of belonging which upholds the 'we-ness' that African continent is known for from antiquity till this contemporary era. With the adoption of participatory kind democracy aided by Mill's utilitarianism in contemporary African socio-political system of governance, it will not only strengthen democracy in various African states such as Nigeria in the western region of Africa, it will also institutionalize a core democratic principle that upholds ethnic unity and tolerance amidst differences in ethnic diversities in African heritage. With this, the utilitarian maxim which states that the greatest good should be of interest of the greatest number of people will be the watchword for the elites at the helms of affairs of many African states in the sub-Saharan Africa.

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